

THE EFFECT OF MULTIMEDIA BASED LEARNING AND CONCEPT MAP OF STUDENT COMPETENCY IN ELECTRIC POWER SYSTEM

Ferry Johnny Sangari,

Syamsul Hadi,

Hary Suswanto

Universitas Negeri Malang, Indonesia

Abstract:

This research discovers the effect of learning model on students' competence in Electrical Power System Analysis Course. This study dealt with experiment group using multimedia learning model consisted of 20 students as a sample subject (A Class) and concept map learning strategy consisted of 23 students as a sample subjects (B Class). The data analysis in this study was using two mean comparative statistics on rate $\alpha = 5\%$. The findings of this research showed that learning model using multimedia improves competences achievement amounted to 32.4%; the failure 1% and score index 3.46. In addition, learning model using map concept improves competences achievement amounted to 26.9%; the failure 5.4% and score index 3.12. Both examined model in this research are significantly different to improve students' competence. Multimedia based learning is confirmed as learning model which improves students' competence more effective than map concept strategy on the significance rate of $\alpha = 5\%$. Furthermore, it is important to conduct a further research which includes students' learning styles as a moderator variable, thus, the interaction of learning model in improving students learning outcome could be discovered.

Keywords: multimedia, map concept, competence, electrical power system analysis

1. Introduction

One of the problems facing Indonesian education today is the weak learning process which resulted in the low quality of education. According to Dasna and Sutrisno (2007),

this is due to the low ability of critical and creative thinking of students. When considered in the learning process students are less encouraged to develop their thinking skills. Learning is directed to memorize and hoard information; therefore, the students are smart in theoretical but poor in applying. As a result, the ability to think critically becomes inferior, even become difficult to develop. Therefore, in the learning process students should be actively encouraged to develop their own knowledge and responsible for the learning outcomes (Gasong, 2006).

Electrical Engineering Education Study Program Faculty of Engineering, State University of Manado, faced problems related to the low learning outcomes of students, particularly in Electrical System Analysis courses. The result of competency test of electric power system study field in the last three years averaged only 15.23% to reach the competent level (A); 62.61% is competent (B); 17.64% less competent (C); And 7.68% incompetent (D & E). This condition is still far from the target set that is the achievement of graduation with a competent level (A) $\geq$ 38%. (Data from PTE Unima Department).

The unfulfilling the intended competency target due to some weaknesses of the students, which includes (1) Lack of mastery about the basic concepts of working principle of electrical system components; (2) Lack of student understanding about power system; (3) Low ability of student to analyze power system Electricity. The weakness is caused by several factors, including the lack of instructional media, the assignment is not constructive, the learning process that does not give enough portion for solving problems in analyzing electrical power system. Learning strategies tend to emphasize the mastery of electrical power system materials. In addition, the low initial ability of students is also a cause of the low learning outcomes achieved, in addition to low learning motivation.

The weaknesses above should not be continued since it will cause a negative impact which lowering the competence of graduates. Moreover, this competency is one of the main competencies in the study program for the field of electric power and is needed in the world of work. Competence of graduates in this field is not only carrying out the analysis or the utilization of the results on the power system, but more than that the competence to design the development of a power system as needed.

Several researches reveal the success of improving students' competence, one of them is through learning using multimedia. Multimedia is able to create an atmosphere and a quality learning climate and improve the competence of learning outcomes in the field of electrical energy (Nortcliffe, & Middleton, 2008; Malik, Mishra, and Shanblatt, 2008; Liao and Ganago, 2011; Watai, Brodersen, and Brophy, 2005; Hohne & Henkel, 2004; Hunt, Howard, Kirk, Ash, & Tyrrell, 2001; Jennings, & Schoch, 1997).

Additionally, Romanas (2007) develops a model of *classic tutorial* multimedia that improves learning outcomes of the electricity sector. Sun Jing and Sun Yafei (2008) develop the field of electrical energy multimedia *tutorial exploratory* models, and is proven to improve learning outcomes. Amjad & Nebras (2012) also develop multimedia for electrical engineering and proves able to improve the competence of learning outcomes significantly.

In addition to multimedia, the implementation of map concept strategy also proves can improve student learning outcomes. Several researches show that low outcomes of learning is due to less understanding upon key concepts or relationships between concepts which students learned (Zheng, *et al*, 2009; McMahon, 2007; Lauglo, 2005). Other studies have also proved that the implementation of map concept strategy can improve learning outcomes (Noprianto, 2006; Kadir, 2004; Rusmansyah, 2001; Isnawati, 2000).

Responding to the low learning outcomes of students, especially in electrical power system analysis courses, it is necessary to innovate learning as an effort to improve the competence of student learning outcomes. Referring to the problem, it is necessary to do learning innovation. From the analysis of characteristics and problems, the use of multimedia learning and application of concept map strategy is considered appropriate to improve student competence in analyzing electric power system.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Learning Outcomes Competence

The competence of learning outcomes in this study can be grouped into three aspects, namely: (1) Understanding the basic concepts and working principles of electrical power system components, (2) Application competence to solve problems of power system, (3) Competence to perform mathematical analysis of power system according to the needs. The study materials covered three topics: (1) Power generators including generators, motors and transformers, (2) Power lines consisting of substations and transmission lines, (3) The distribution and loads of power systems.

Figure 1: Concept map of electric power system course

2.2 Learning Model Based on Multimedia

Multimedia-based learning refers to the theory of cognitivism that develops in two approaches namely objectivism and constructivism (Su, 2009). From this theory developed the theory of information processing (Driscoll, 2005; Ormrod, 2004). Cognitive processes occur in the human brain from receiving, processing and storing information as well as summoning information back from the brain (Schunk, 2004). In the theory of working memory Baddeley (2009), there are four main components, namely *visuospatial Sketchpad*, *episodic buffer*, *phonological loop* and the *central executive*.

The learning process will be more effective if using instructional media developed in visual and auditory form (Wouters, Fred Paas & Merriënboer, 2008). This is the principle of multimedia learning, that humans can learn more easily when learning materials which are delivered in visual and auditory form compared to spoken language (Mayer, 2014). This concept is in accordance with the *dual-coding* theory of Paivio (2006) that the student will receive the optimum material if it involves the teaching of the association between the sense of sight (visual) with the sense of hearing (auditory). Learning outcomes will be more effective if the learning process using multimedia tools.

Multimedia cognitive theory (*Cognitive theory of multimedia learning*) from Clark & Mayer (2008) is a combination of *cognitive load theory* of Sweller, *Dual-coding theory* of Pavio and *Working memory models* of Baddeley (Mayer, 2014). Information processing takes place in three important stages: choosing the appropriate material, preparing the selected material and combining it with the knowledge already held. The material selection process occurs when individuals pay attention to the material delivered through multimedia, and bring it into working memory in the cognitive system.

The process of preparing the selected materials is done through the selection of materials in working memory. Furthermore, the integration of materials that have been prepared with the knowledge that has been previously owned from long-term memory to working memory. The flow of information processing is expressed in the cognitive model of multimedia learning theory as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Multimedia Cognitive Learning Theory (Clark & Mayer, 2008)

This learning model sets out four principles of research in cognitive science (Clark and Mayer, 2008): (1) *Dual channel*, humans process information visual form or image and auditory or verbal in a separate channel, (2) *Limited capacity*, humans can actively process only on some part of information in each channel on one particular time, (3) *active processing*, learning occurs when individuals involved in cognitive processes, such as attention to the relevant material, organizing the material into the structure coherent, and integrate with the knowledge they already information, (4) *Transfer* of new knowledge and skills must be taken of long-term memory during the process.

Multimedia based learning is based on the principle of tutorial. Effective multimedia learning needs to take at least six major aspects, namely: (1) *access*; (2) *cost*; (3) *technology*; (4) *interactivity*; (5) *organization* and (6) *novelty* (Kusnandar, 2003). Good instructional media must meet the requirements. Wahono (2007) divides multimedia-based instructional media in three aspects: (1) Software engineering aspects; (2) Aspects of instructional design and (3) Aspects of visual communication.

Multimedia as a teaching instrument as well as a source of learning will be more effective if the teaching material is designed according to the rules. The sequence of learning is structured in accordance with the objectives to be achieved. The selection of material sequences is not a complete list, but is the most indispensable material in the curriculum.

Learning material in the form of tutorial media is designed in accordance with the seven following groups which include (1) *Classic tutorial*, (2) *Activity centered tutorial*, (3) *Learner customized tutorial*, (4) *Knowledge-based tutorial*, (5) *Exploratory tutorial*, (6) *Drill & practice tutorial* dan juga (7) *Generated lesson tutorial* (Thomas, 2005; Horton, 2000). In addition multimedia learning is conducted based on the following flow chart in the figure below.

Figure 3: Multimedia-based Learning Model

Multimedia-based learning procedure begins with the initial test to determine the ability before following the lesson. Furthermore, the orientation of learning give guidance regarding the learning process using multimedia to be implemented. The learning process in this multimedia model is done by learning face to face and followed by learning tutorial using instructional multimedia for each individual using developed multimedia. Multimedia contains teaching materials in the form of text, visual, auditory, video and animation with the target ability of understanding, reasoning, application and analysis. After completion one unit of learning, final test is conducted.

2.3 Concept Map Strategy

Learning strategy using concept maps emphasizes the fundamental cognitive aspects of the concept and the characteristics of the objects studied. The concept is a necessary condition for mastering the skills of prior discrimination and fundamental cognitive processes based on the similarity of features of a collection of stimuli and objects (Djamarah & Zain, 2002). Novak (2005) emphasizes concept maps as tools or strategies to help students organize lecture concepts learned based on their meaning and relationships. The relationship of one concept (information) to another is known as a proposition, which is two or more concepts connected by words in a semantic unit.

Learning strategy using map concept is done to give meaning to what is learned. Concept maps have five characteristics: (1) *branches*; (2) *arrows*; (3) *grouping*; (4) *list*, and (5) *the explanatory notes*. Concepts expressed in terms of concept terms or labels are woven meaningfully with the connecting words that form propositions. One proposition contains two concepts and connecting words. One concept has a wider scope (inclusive) than any other concept.

Furthermore, a more inclusive concept placed on a less inclusive concept is then linked. A more specific concept is placed underneath, linked again to the connector. An

inclusive concept can be attributed to some less inclusive concepts. The most inclusive concept is placed at the top of the concept tree, called the key concept. The concept of one path can be related to the concept of another path with the conjunctive term, and this relationship is called crosslinking which shows the integration of the development paths in the discussion called integrative adjustment.

The concept map strategy estimates the depth and extent of material that needs to be learned. The correlation of one concept with another concept is important in learning therefore what is learned will be more meaningful, easier to remember and understand, and processed and reissued when necessary (Trianto, 2009, Nasution, 2008). This will improve learning outcomes through a more meaningful process of the material being studied. For educators, the concept map strategy is useful for (1) helping to do what is known, plan and start a learning topic, and process keywords to be used. (2) Helping to recall and revise learning concepts, create work record patterns and learn good. (3) Helping to diagnose what is known in the form of structure. (4) Helping to identify misconceptions, for example in the exam will depict the ability to process the idea in the form of graphics or the use of a representative visual. (5) Helping to check understanding of learned concepts, concept maps that are made are correct or still wrong. (6) Helping to improve concept errors in subsequent learning. (7) Helping to plan learning and evaluation of success (Rusmansyah, 2001).

For students, the concept map strategy is useful to: (1) assist the identification of key concepts, estimate the relationships of understanding and help further learning. (2) Help to make the concept of lessons better for exam purposes. (3) Help to provide thoughts relating learning concepts. (4) Help to think with ideas and make them understand the true knowledge. (5) Clarify ideas obtained regarding something in the form of description. (6) Create a structure of understanding how all new and existing facts are connected with subsequent knowledge. (7) Assist learning activities on how to organize things from information, facts and concepts into a context of understanding, so as to establish correct understanding.

Concept maps there are four kinds, namely (1) *Network tree*; (2) *Event chain*; (3) *Cycle Concept map*; (4) *Spider concept map* (Nur, 2002). The preparation of concept maps is needed in the learning process hence learners know and believe about the meaning of what is being learned, and can arrange in a relatively short time interspersed with other work while thinking about the inter-linkage of concepts to form a proposition that makes learning more meaningful.

There are seven steps to follow in order to create a concept map correctly, namely: (1) Selecting and defining a reading material; (2) the reading material may be selected from a book or other reading material; (3) determining relevant concepts; (4)

sorting concepts from the most general to the most specialized or examples; (5) arranging concepts, mapping out the criteria of the most common concepts at the top, concepts at the level of abstraction parallel to one another, and the concept more specifically under the more general concept; (6) linking concepts with certain connecting words to form propositions and connecting lines; (7) after the map is complete, it is necessary to look again at where the concepts are and if necessary it can be improved or rearranged to be better and meaningful.

2.4 Learning with Concept Map

Implementation of the learning model in this study was developed in two phases of learning. The first phase is the process of regular teaching learning by classical learning using a combination of learning methods in accordance with the learning materials (regular or conventional face-to-face lessons). The second phase is assigning tasks to students in the form of concept maps of lecture materials that have been discussed in the lecturing. The assignment is done in groups with about 5 people each group. The results of the group work for concept map development will be presented in face-to-face lectures and addressed by other groups. The result of this concept map mapping is summarized into a common conclusion.

After several units of lectures are presented then the formative test is conducted. The analysis of student achievement outcomes as an input for improvement in the next lecture. At the last meeting, the final test to determine the achievements of student learning outcomes developed with a concept map strategy is conducted. The learning process with the model implementation of concept map strategy is expressed as the following figure.

Gambar 3: Disain pembelajaran dengan strategi peta konsep

3. Methodology

The research was conducted using quasi experiments, with the students participating in the Analysis of Electrical Power System Course as respondents. There are two groups of

experiments in this study, experiment group using multimedia-based learning (X_1) and concept map learning strategy (X_2). The test instrument developed refers to the competencies according to the curriculum, and validity of reliability, difficulty and distinguishing level were tested. Learning outcomes (Y) as the dependent variable obtained through achievement test, i.e. *gain score of the final test* and *pre-test* and will compared between the two groups. The data analysis using Z-test (*two-tail test*), on the level of $\alpha = 5\%$ after the required test particularly on the normality and homogeneity (Supranto 2008; Harinaldi, 2005).

4. Findings and Discussion

Students' learning outcomes in electric power system course is quite good in both learning models. Within multimedia-based learning, it obtained index of $X_1 = 3,46$ which the minimum score (less competent or C) amounted to 5.3% and the maximum score (highly competent or A) amounted to 30%, meanwhile, students' learning accomplishment was 99%. The result is presented in the following Table 1. In concept maps learning strategy, it obtained index of $X_2 = 3.12$ which the minimum score (failed or E) amounted to 5.6% and the maximum score (highly competent or A) amounted to 30%, meanwhile, students' learning accomplishment was 93.6%. The result is presented in the following Table 2.

Table 1: Multimedia Learning Outcomes Using Multimedia-based Learning

		Freq	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	C = 2.0	1	5.0	2.6
	C+ = 2.5	1	5.0	5.3
	B = 3.0	5	25.0	28.9
	B+ = 3.5	7	35.0	65.8
	A = 4.0	6	30.0	100.0
	Total	20	100.0	
Mean		3.46		
Median		3.50		
Mode		3.50		
Std. Dev.		0.475		
Minimum		2.0		
Maximum		4.0		

Tabel 2: Multimedia Learning Outcomes Using Multimedia-based Learning

		Freq	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	E = 0.00	1	4.3	4.3
	C = 2.0	2	8.7	13.9
	C+ = 2.5	2	8.7	22.2
	B = 3.0	5	21.7	47.2
	B+ = 3.5	5	21.7	72.2
	A = 4.0	8	34.9	100.0
	Total	23	100.0	
Mean		3.12		
Median		3.50		
Mode		4.00		
Std. Dev.		0.878		
Minimum		0.00		
Maximum		4.00		

The accomplishment of student's competence in electrical power system analysis course is indicated improving significantly as shown in Table 3.

Tabel 3: Learning Outcomes Competence Accomplishment

Competencies	Competence Aspect					
	Basic Concept		Application		Analysis	
	MM	PK	MM	PK	MM	PK
Generator	84	86	85	82	78	75
Transmission	78	82	86	84	75	74
Distribution	83	85	88	85	80	76
Mean	81.76	83.34	86.43	82.56	78.76	76.00

In the aspect of competence, the basic concept of learning model using concept map strategy is more effective compared to learning using multimedia, that is 83.34 to 81.76, but on application aspect to solve problems and mathematical analysis precisely multimedia-based learning is much more effective with achievement of learning result, higher than the learning with the concept map strategy that is with the average of 86.43 and 78.76 versus 82.56 and 76.00 both for material related to generator, transmission and also the distribution of electric power.

If the competence of the learning outcomes of the two models are compared, the results show that there is a significant difference in learning achievement outcomes of both models, at 95% confidence level. This difference shows that multimedia-based learning model is more effective in improving the capability of achievement of student

learning outcomes in Electrical System Analysis course. The summary of test results is shown in Table 4 and Table 5 below.

Table 4: Learning Outcomes Statistics of Two Learning Model

	Learning Model	N	Mean	SD	SE Mean
Learning outcomes	Multimedia	20	3.46	0.475	0.78
	Concept maps	23	3.12	0.878	1.63

Table 5: Two-Mean Comparative Testing

		Lev Test for EV		t-test for Equality of Means		
		F	Sig	t	df	Sig
Learning outcomes	Equal variances assumed	7.03	010	2.12	72	0.39
	Equal variances not assumed			2.07	50.64	0.43

Multimedia-based learning model is the first independent variable implemented quasi experiments with a sample of 20 people. The result of the research found that the average of learning result 3,46 whereas in the learning model with the implementation of concept map strategy with 23 respondents get the average of learning result 3,12.

Comparative test results on the level of $\alpha = 5\%$ yth obtained value of 2.12 where it is significant due to the significance of test results below 0.05. Thus, research has proven that multimedia-based learning can improve student learning outcomes in electrical power system analysis courses. Multimedia learning model is more effective in an effort to improve the capabilities of learning outcomes compared with the learning model using concept maps, and at the level of 95% confidence, the results is accepted very significant.

Furthermore, it is compared with the existing performance indicator and the accomplishment of results. It is shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Performance Indicator Accomplishment

No	Performance Indicator	Base Line	Accomplishment		Note
			MM	CM	
1	Competent (A)	13.2%	32.4%	26.9%	Improved
2	Failed (E)	8.81%	1%	5.4%	Declined
3	Score Index	2.92	3.46	3.12	Improved

Table 6 shows that the two instructional learning model are proven able to improve learning outcomes of Electrical Power System Analysis Course. On the multimedia-based learning model, it is able to improve students learning outcome and achieve competent category (A) amounted to 32.4% from 13.3% baseline, and for failed students only 1%. Meanwhile score index improves from 2.92 to 3.46. Likewise, learning with concept map strategy is also able to increase the achievement of learning outcomes with 26.9% succeeded in reaching the competent level (A) from the baseline of 13.2%, and decreasing the student failed to 5.4% from the 8.81% baseline and raising the value index to 3.12 from baseline 2.92. Although compared to multimedia-based learning is still lower but overall this concept maps model can improve the learning achievement capability achieved by the students compared with the baseline so far.

The failure of students as much as 5.4% in learning concept map strategy is caused more by the weakness of the ability of students, particularly in understanding abstract and conceptual events which is difficult to apply in problem solving (analysis), in addition to describe the sequence of system troubleshooting procedures Electric power.

5. Conclusion

Multimedia-based and concept map strategy have advantages in an effort to improve learning outcomes in Electrical System Analysis courses, especially on competency aspects of mathematical analysis of electrical power systems. Compared to the conventional learning baseline, multimedia-based learning model proved able to improve learning outcomes with an achievement gain of A as much as 22% from the baseline, 99% graduation completion and a 0.54 accomplishment grade index increase.

In learning with concept map strategy is also able to increase learning achievement of competent level 14,6% from baseline, and decrease failure rate 3,12% and increase value index equal to 0,12 from baseline. However, this model is still lower in effectiveness compared to the multimedia-based learning model, both in the achievement of competency level, the decrease of percentage of failure and also the increase of the index of the value of the course.

Given some limitations in this study, for further research it is also necessary to study student learning style as a moderator variable, because in reality this learning style also influences student's learning effectiveness both on multimedia-based learning and on learning by applying concept map strategy. Thus, the influence of learning styles and interaction with learning model that refers to the achievement of learning result capability can be revealed.

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